

Ending AIDS: a Global Public Good

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1 Introduction

The International Task Force on Global Public Goods has defined global public goods (GPG) as issues that are broadly conceived as important to the international community, that for the most part cannot or will not be adequately addressed by individual countries acting alone and that are defined through a broad international consensus or a legitimate process of decision-making(1). Five domains for GPG have been identified amongst which is preventing the emergence and spread of infectious disease, which includes HIV. The *response to HIV* can be defined as the global commitment by all nations to scale up response to achieve broad multisectoral coverage for prevention, treatment, care and support, as described in the United Nations Political Declaration on HIV/AIDS(2). Responding to the HIV epidemic requires strong leadership and sustained commitment and concerted efforts on the part of all stakeholders at all levels. But what makes HIV so specific as an epidemic is that it is a long wave event that goes beyond health issues and includes caring for orphan and vulnerable children, ensuring food and nutritional support, social protection, as well as human rights and fundamental freedoms for all.

As a global public good, the commitment towards HIV faces six clear challenges that have economic implications: its provision, its delivery systems, the sovereignty of States, the segmentation of the global response, the necessity to first control the epidemic and the price protection resulting from intellectual property rights.

This study will go through those six challenges of the response to HIV; with particular attention to the provision of HIV programmes and its main economic challenges. Economic theory provides rationales for why a global public good such as the HIV response can be under-funded. There are fundamental asymmetries between countries, and regions that are most in need of the response to HIV as a global public good are often those that can afford it the least. This circumstance underlines why, in addition to humanist and ethical considerations, the global response to the HIV epidemic will remain an exceptional global public good for decades. The paper introduces an innovative framework for the possible financing mechanisms for HIV for the long term. Finally, the paper asks the question whether the global response to HIV provides positive externalities, in addition to its primary goal of meeting the Sustainable Development Goals.

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2 The theory of public goods

a) *What are private and public goods?*

Economic theory⁽³⁾ distinguishes between *private* and *public* goods in a very specific way. The distinction depends on two main attributes:

1. Whether there is “rivalry” in the consumption of the good – i.e. does its use by one individual diminish its availability for another individual?
2. Whether the benefits of the good are “excludable” – i.e. is it possible, at reasonable cost, to prevent its consumption by those who have not paid for it, or are not intended to receive it?

A *private good* is one that has rivalry in its consumption, and is excludable in its benefits. A *public good* is the opposite – it is “non-rival” in its consumption, and “non-excludable” in its benefits. Atmosphere, sunlight or a lighthouse are generally cited as “pure” public goods. A national campaign with posters on HIV is a public good because a person seeing the advertising does not prevent others from seeing it and nobody passing by can be excluded from seeing it.

The economic concept of a public good is not the same as what is usually meant by “the public good”, which refers to an ethical distinction between what is good opposed to what is bad for society. It is also important to understand that public goods are not necessarily goods provided by the public sector (although this might often be the case). Public goods may be privately produced, produced through collective action, or be naturally available.

b) *How clear is the criterion of rivalry?*

By these criteria, antiretroviral drugs (ARV) might be regarded as private goods. Drugs used by one individual are no longer available for anyone else and the immediate benefit is experienced by the person who takes them. However, it can also be argued that this benefit extends to some extent to the family and community of the person being treated. The criteria are therefore not always unambiguous. In practice, the criterion of rivalry is usually reasonably clear – most purchased goods are rival, whereas universally available goods such as sunshine or air are not. However, the scarcity of a good creates rivalry in its consumption if there is a limited capacity to produce it. For example, the use of a health facility will become more and more rival as the number of patients increases towards the limits of the capacity of the facility.

c) *The role of policy in modifying excludability*

There is a wider range of degrees to which goods can be said to be excludable. The degree is subject to several factors that can be modified, for example:

- *Policy choices*: A government might decide to make a good more or less available. Its policy choice might favor one geographical area or a group of people.
- *Access constraints*: The availability of factors that constrain access to the public good. For example the availability of well functioning health facilities or the ability to maintain a cold chain is necessary in order to deliver antiretroviral drugs. Income levels may also constrain access for the poorest people.
- *Administrative constraints*. A requirement for registration as a precondition might act as a constraint to access for some communities or groups not recognized by the authorities, such

as injecting drug users or men who have sex with men. Lack of confidentiality regarding sero-status of individuals would also fall into this category.

For these reasons, most public goods are “impure” public goods *i.e.* at least one of the two conditions is not fully met. For example, even where ARV treatment is provided free of charge, its limited supply means that access to treatment becomes partly rival.

If a good is non-excludable, then the concept of *free-riding* becomes possible – people can take the benefit of the good without paying for its production. Once a pure public good is available for all, it is not possible -or suitable to exclude anyone from consuming it. Therefore, individuals are less likely to respond to changes to price, and private providers will not produce at the optimal level.

In our day-to-day life, goods do not necessarily correspond neatly to the two criteria. What should be kept in mind is that the criterion of non-rivalry is inherent to a public good, while the criterion of non-excludability is relative. Price mechanisms, regulations or even policy choices can deprive or allow an individual from accessing a public good. Thus, excludability can be modified by policy. The extent to which a community or a nation can make the benefit of a public good more or less excludable is a societal issue.

The two criteria for defining public and private goods lead to a four-way classification illustrated in the following table.

Table 1: Basic properties of Public goods

	Excludable	Non-Excludable
Rival	<p>Private Goods</p> <p>Access is regulated by the willingness to produce and willingness to consume determined by prices and market forces.</p> <p>For example, in most countries food, clothing, cars etc. are private goods.</p>	<p>Common goods</p> <p>Access is limited by shortage. For example clean air, drinking water and all limited natural resources.</p> <p>This combination often leads to excess consumption (partly because of free riding) and to wasting of the limited resource.</p> <p>Governments and communities generally react in making the good partly excludable, using for example property rights, permits or rules, to regulate its consumption.</p>
Non-Rival	<p>Club goods</p> <p>Access is limited to selected people. For example goods only available to those who subscribe – such as satellite television.</p> <p>This can also apply to goods that can only be afforded by people above a certain income level. In many countries, second</p>	<p>Public goods</p> <p>This combination applies to “pure” public goods such as air and sunshine that are naturally available, but also to goods such as advertising (including public health messages), or to free state broadcasting</p>

<p>line ARV can become a club good for this reason.</p> <p>In all cases, the exclusion of some consumers implies that total demand will be below its optimal market level, leading to less production of the good.</p>	
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d) *Public goods and market failure*

Public goods are not optimally provided by a free market, principally because of the free rider problem caused by non-excludability. Private sector producers will not willingly supply public goods because they cannot be sure of making an economic return. As a consequence, the market for public goods, if left alone, will always lead either to unsatisfied demand or to production below the optimal level. In economic language, we can say that the normal operations of market forces will not lead to market efficiency, where the marginal cost of producing one unit of the good would be the same as the marginal willingness-to-pay of consumers.. The effective provision of public goods therefore requires some form of intervention in order to provide incentives, or to regulate consumption in some way.

e) *Health as a public good*

The Macroeconomic Commission for Health(4) (CMH) looked at the question of whether or not health is a public good. From an economic point of view, health might be called a private good. One's health status is exclusive and it is maintained mainly from private goods (drugs, housing, food). Nevertheless, good health confers benefits to the whole of society – higher productivity, better resistance to epidemics and so on. For this reason, the CMH concluded that public health could be considered as a public good. Governments are creating incentives, regulations or directly finance interventions that²:

- 1- Have a positive impact on health that exceeds the impact individuals can accomplish if they do it on their own;
- 2- Regulate activities of individuals that can harm the health condition of others, for example campaign against smoking in public spaces;
- 3- Promote individuals' health in situations that go beyond private health itself, for example health and safety in the workplace;
- 4- Promote the health of the general population, for example by regulating chemical use in agriculture or disposal of industrial waste.

3 Global public goods

a) *Definition of a global public good*

The globalization of the world economy has brought new challenges, opportunities and constraints within the health and other sectors. For example, globalization provides opportunities to expand research networks, to improve worldwide epidemiological surveillance, and to provide better and wider application of the convention on health-related hazards.

² See the report of working group 2 of the CMH (2002) for more details on the specific issue of Public health.

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The theory of public goods(3) has evolved accordingly. The idea of a Global Public Good (GPG) refers to a public good that is available globally. The key difference between this and the definition at a country level is the absence of a *world government* to coerce or to create incentives in order to compensate the market irregularity of a global public good. Furthermore, any attempt would quickly encroach on the principle of sovereignty of the different states.

There is no single definition of a global public good (GPG). Some definitions are more inclusive, while others stress operational concerns of the supply and demand of the good. Four views are presented here:

- Kaul et al(5, 6) defined a GPG as a public good with benefits that are strongly universal in terms of countries (covering more than one group of countries), people (accruing to several or all population groups) and generations (extending to both current and future generations, or at least meeting the needs of current generations without compromising options for future generations).
- Morrissey et al(7) provided a more utilitarian definition when defining international public good as a benefit providing a benefit that is available, in principle, to everybody throughout the globe.
- Barrett(8) suggested focusing more on the operational aspects of those “goods whose supply depends critically on international collective action, even though they may not be fully global (they may be regional) and have some excludability or rivalry”³.
- The International Task Force on Global Public Goods(1) defined global public goods as "issues that are broadly conceived as important to the international community, that for the most part cannot or will not be adequately addressed by individual countries acting alone and that are defined through a broad international consensus or a legitimate process of decision-making."

The latter definition enabled the ITFGPG to focus on five domains for global public goods:

1. Preventing the emergence and spread of infectious disease;
2. Tackling climate change;
3. Promoting financial stability and international trade;
4. Achieving peace and security; and
5. Generating knowledge (a cross-cutting good).

For global public goods; their *provision* is probably the main issue to consider here. Any individual or nation motivated by rational self-interest would “free ride”, meaning they would prefer to take the benefit of the good and let others bear the cost of it. Regardless of this, if nations get penalized for not making the public good available, they will produce it, but at a level below the optimum. The production of a global public good, particularly the HIV response, encounters five other challenges: the sovereignty of States; the delivery systems of HIV response; the segmentation of the global response; the necessity to control the epidemic instead of eradicating it and the price protection

³ One might stress that, due to the characteristics of the epidemic, the intergenerational component has a particular importance and should not be taken away from the definition of a global public good.

resulting from the intellectual property rights. The next sections will present those six issues with an emphasis on the provision of the Response to HIV as a global public good.

b) The response to HIV as a global public good

We have seen that preventing the emergence and spread of infectious disease has been defined as a global public good. Responding to the HIV epidemic reflects a global commitment expressed in the 2006 United Nations Political Declaration on HIV/AIDS. Following this Declaration, all countries committed themselves to pursue all necessary efforts to scale up responses to achieve broad multisectoral coverage for prevention, treatment, care and support. Responding to the epidemic requires intervention in all sectors of society; from human rights to education, from health to economics; from agriculture to sociology.

As for most GPG, the response to HIV faces the challenge of its provision. At global level, this challenge is enhanced by the fact that the marginal willingness-to-pay differs from one country to another. People place a different value on the benefit of the good. Those differences comprise cultural, economic, social and financial considerations for which each country is sovereign. Further, the preferences of Governments are not uniform, and are subject to changes over time. Preferences are due to various factors, economic, sociological, cultural or religious. The ways these preferences are translated into priorities then differ as well. For example, the non-recognition of sex-workers or homosexuality in some countries will substantially change the way the country responds to HIV.

Countries are also asymmetric in their capacity to benefit from global public goods. Moreover, some countries do not have the capacity-to-pay or to produce the good, regardless of their willingness-to-pay. This is the situation that many sub-Saharan countries are facing with the response to the HIV epidemic. This will be further discussed later in this chapter.

From a macroeconomic point of view, the impact of the epidemic at country level is estimated to around 1 – 1,5 % of economic growth in least developed countries with high HIV burden⁴. However, this figure does not take into account the long-run erosion of human capital which introduces an intergenerational component of impact in the longer term⁵.

The response to HIV therefore brings both short term and long-term returns. Prevention activities or activities in favor of orphans and vulnerable children aim to slow and reverse the course of the epidemic and thereby invest in tomorrow's healthy human capital. Providing care and treatment enables people living with HIV to live a normal life and to keep their place in the community and economy – whether or not their activities are monetized

Therefore, all countries, low or high income are concerned with the epidemic regardless of the country's time preference.

4 The challenges of the response to HIV as a global public good

As stated earlier, the response to HIV faces six clear challenges: its provision, sovereignty of States, its delivery systems, the segmentation of the global response, the necessity to control the epidemic

⁴ See UN Economic and Social Affairs Department, Population Division (2004)

⁵ See Bell, Devarajan and Gersbach (2003)

instead of eradicating it and the price protection resulting from intellectual property rights. These are further discussed below.

a) The provision of the global response to HIV

The provision of the response to HIV can be described as a coordination game: countries are expected to contribute to where their willingness-to-pay equals the marginal benefit that they expect to receive from the good. The result of this situation is that countries are aware of the benefits of a successful global response to HIV and are keen of taking advantage of it but there is under-funding of the effort. Strong political commitment is needed to reinforce and encourage the willingness-to-pay of all actors.

i) The production technology of the response to HIV

Economists have further characterized global public goods according to the way in which they are produced, i.e. the *production technology* (Hirshleifer 1983). This aspect of a GPG has important implications for expectations about the probable level of funding, and for the way countries organize their respective contributions to provide the GPG. What makes HIV a particularly complex global public good is that the response is made of 70 main activities⁶ relating to different sectors of intervention. As a result, responding to HIV do not fall into one single production technology. Each production technology is presented below and examples corresponding to different sectors are presented.

Summation processes

The provision of ARV treatment is an example of a *summation process*, because the total number of people receiving treatment is simply the sum of those receiving treatment in each country. Many global public goods are produced by this type of process, meaning that the collective outcome is the sum of the individual efforts of countries (CMH 2002). This principle also applies to public education about how HIV is transmitted – the total amount of knowledge transmitted is the sum of the efforts of those providing it.

In general, the contributors to the production of a GPG with a summation technology face a “prisoner’s dilemma”. This means that the best solution is obtained when all parties cooperate, but there is the possibility of free riding – i.e. a country that does not cooperate will gain at the expense of the others. This is referred to as a “coordination game”. The net result is that since free riding cannot be eliminated, the production of GPG of this kind is expected to be under-funded.

Weighted sum processes

For some GPG, the different contributions do not have the same impact as each other, and they cannot be substituted. For example, identical prevention interventions in different countries will not have the same effectiveness, because of differences in cultural practices and patterns of the epidemic. In general, this is referred to as a *weighted sum* technology, which applies to a large part of the HIV prevention effort.

In this case, the contributors face a mixture of circumstances, since the benefits of the GPG are not distributed equally, and different countries do not have the same ability-to-pay. In the case of the response to HIV, there is a perverse relationship between impact of HIV and ability-to-pay. Countries more affected by HIV and its impacts will have an incentive to contribute a larger share, but are

⁶ See UNAIDS, 2007b, National AIDS Spending Assessment (NASA): Classification Tables & Definitions

unable to do so. Countries in Western Europe and North America are less affected, and will have the incentive to contribute only up to what they perceive to be their marginal benefit – which is less than their ability-to-pay. The net result is also the theoretical expectation that the production of a GPG of this kind will be under-funded.

Better or best shot processes

Research for an HIV vaccine is highly technical, and is best carried out by a specialized agency with the resources to do it. This is an example of a *best shot* technology where the collective outcome equals that of the largest contributor. Small additional efforts have limited impact on the overall outcome.

The contributors to this kind of process face a form of what is called the “chicken game”, which means that the optimal solution is reached when one party “yields” and pays for the production of the GPG, although no party has the incentive to do so. However, all countries lose if none of them yields.

In practice, this can also be solved by cooperation. In this specific example, the different contributors have agreed to provide joint funding to the International AIDS Vaccine Initiative to conduct and coordinate the research efforts.

Weaker or weakest link processes

The converse of this is the *weakest link* technology, meaning that the collective outcome equals that of the smallest contributor. It can be argued that this applies to the epidemiological surveillance of the epidemic, since the strength of the surveillance network is limited by the strength of the country having the lowest surveillance capacity. It may apply also in general to the HIV prevention component. With globalization and the increased circulation of people, the outcome of effective prevention worldwide is to some extent limited by the level of the lowest contributors.

Contributors to a weakest link process face a form of what is known as an “assurance game” in which countries must make a choice to invest without knowing whether others will cooperate by investing similarly – if others do not, the benefit of one country’s investment may be nullified by negative developments in other countries.

In this case, it is in the interest of the international community to support the weakest countries and regions to deliver effective prevention and surveillance. The weakest link production technology should be less problematic in terms of financing as there is generally an incentive for developed countries in supporting the contributions of less developed countries. If countries perceived the response to HIV to be a weakest link process, then we might expect that the response would be adequately financed.

ii) Threshold processes

A *threshold* process refers to the situation where the benefits from the GPG are only apparent if the level of provision is above a particular threshold. This can be said to apply to many different components of HIV prevention, such as outreach to sex workers or injecting drug users, where the intervention is only effective in reducing HIV incidence once the coverage level is sufficiently high. This means that a partial response is in some respects the same as no response at all, and the level of investment is wasted.

A threshold process implies a need for global coordination similar to the “assurance game” implied by the weakest link processes – it is in the global interest to ensure adequate investment in all countries, and the global outcome is compromised by countries that default.

iii) The financing mechanisms of the response to HIV

As we have seen, a successful response to HIV requires considerable international cooperation, where poorer and more affected countries are expected to contribute as much as they are able, while wealthier and less affected countries are expected to contribute beyond what they perceive to be their marginal benefit.

Because resources are limited and capability to contribute is different, these create incentives for substitution effects. We identified three levels of substitution effects in financing mechanisms for HIV programs.

Substitution between national and global response

A first strategic substitution effect could apply as a result of the response at country-level: A country providing a successful national program for HIV and experiencing a decline of HIV incidence inside its border might perceive that it can lower its global contribution to HIV since the epidemic appears to be less harmful for its citizens. In other terms, national and global public goods may be substitutes (Barrett 1999).

Strong political commitments at global level are necessary to avoid strategic substitution. It would create and maintain the momentum amongst successful countries to continue supporting global provision to HIV, even when the epidemic is under control at their national level. Not doing so will leave countries that are least able to respond at national level the most vulnerable to the infection.

Substitution among channels for financing

In economic theory, the *neutrality theorem* predicts that, for a pure global public good financed on voluntary basis, any increase from one contributor crowds out voluntary contributions from others. In other terms, a country contribution to a global public good is a substitute for another country's one. The degree of substitutability depends on how pure is the global public good (Sandler and Arce 2002a). Van Dalen (2005) studied OECD official development assistance for reproductive health and HIV programs. From 1983 to 2002, he found no evidence of such a crowding-out effect from one donor to another⁷. Van Dalen results are interesting but additional empirical work are needed using 2002-2007 data on aid, from when the Response to HIV significantly increased with GFATM and PEPFAR, leading to potential change in donors' behavior.

In addition, Sandler and Arce (2002a) also highlighted that countries contributing to a global public good through a multilateral organization are most likely to reduce their direct voluntary contribution to the good and rely on what the organization will supply⁸. In other words, bilateral and multilateral contributions may be substitutes. With regard to HIV:

⁷ More precisely, his results suggest that donor countries are not affected by what other bilateral donors give. Only the situation inside the donor country itself affects its funding and the situation of the poor countries has no statistical impact on the amount of aid.

⁸ Sandler and Arce pointed that countries are facing a budget constraint and in order to maintain their well-being, they should subtract their multilateral contributions from their bilateral contribution to give.

- First, it would limit the options for multilateral organizations to increase the provision for HIV. Requesting more from *usual* contributing bilateral donors through their multilateral channel could lead to a crowding-out of their respective supply of the response through bilateral channels, leading to a zero net increase. In order to minimize this risk, Sandler and Arce (2002b) suggest focusing subsequent rounds of donation on previous non-contributors so that a net increase in overall supply can be possible. This highlights the economic importance of philanthropic foundations and non-governmental organizations (NGO).
- Second, the importance of multilateral organizations like UNAIDS that generate and maintain the participation of all stakeholders but are not themselves a supranational organization actually providing the global public good⁹. The provision of the global response to HIV is participatory and voluntary, and the coordination role is vital since coercion or regulation is not appropriate as it might be for other global public goods such as achieving peace and security.

Substitution or complementarity with Official Development Assistance

The link between global public goods and development aid seems logical, given the need for higher contributions from countries with greater ability-to-pay. However, literature often points out that most least developed countries are concerned about substitution – that financing of GPG in this way might reduce the level of development aid available for other purposes¹⁰. The purpose of this section is not to solve this debate but rather to provide keys for the analysis of the relationship between global public goods and official development assistance (ODA).

Typically, global public good benefits are generated over a medium to long term whereas official development assistance is usually designed to provide short to medium term relief (with the expectation of sustainable results). Low income countries generally have a high time preference rate, meaning that they look to aid to provide the resources needed for urgent improvements to their living conditions and economic development.

The response to HIV meets both short and long-term considerations. Scaling up care and treatment enables people to return to their economic activity and meet their livelihood needs. At the same time, the benefits of prevention and research activities are expected over a longer time horizon.

The relationship between development and global public goods is in both directions. Development investments that increase the supply of health services in a country are needed to respond successfully to HIV. In the other direction, providing ARV treatment enables people to reintegrate into the labor market. This implies that ODA should enter in the provision of a global public good where national capacities to contribute or benefit from the good are weak. In the case of the response to HIV, this could include activities such as strengthening health facilities, training health technicians, reviewing national legislation currently hindering access to services, or using TRIPS flexibility for building ARV production.

Most discourses argue for additional international funding for global public goods. Kanbur and Sandler (1999) raised the issue as to whether or not international public goods should be financed

⁹ Some other multilateral institutions have been created for the purpose of a global public good. Those agencies provide services that can themselves be considered as global public good. WTO, WIPO and the IMF in its initial mandate.

¹⁰ See among other International Task Force on Global Public Goods (2006), Marniesse (2005) and Sagasti and Bezanson (2001)

through aid. They argued that “there are indeed significant interactions between international public goods -like the spread of AIDS- and development. Through these interactions, a case can be made for financing international public goods as development assistance.”

iv) The need for innovative mechanisms for financing the response to HIV

Sagasti and Bezanson (2001) presented a first framework of the mechanisms¹¹ for financing international or global public goods. Lamontagne and Greener (2008) proposed a framework for the financing options specifically for HIV. The framework is centered on the low and middle income countries as their needs exceed the resources available for most of them. The framework on next page provides a schematic synthesis. The different possibilities presented are not mutually exclusive but complementary with the others. Combinations open the gate to different degrees of partnership opportunities. This kind of framework provides a starting point for analysis by Governments and multilateral agencies for each country case.

The research for HIV, particularly regarding vaccine development, highlights a specific case.

Under the assumption of a vaccine that would sufficiently protect its bearer from being infected, such a protection benefit corresponds to an externality. This individual externality could be *internalized* by charging a suitable price for the immunization, which would also serve to compensate the producer for the costs of research. This is probably the only case of internalizing an externality for the response HIV. In such a case, the challenge would be to ensure availability of a vaccine early-on and avoid it being treated as a “private” or “club” good, as was initially the case with first line ARV. Kremer (2001a and 2001b) and Sagasti and Bezanson (2001) suggested that this might be avoided through a commitment by multilateral organizations or developed countries to purchase effective vaccines once they are available.

Feasibility of different financing mechanisms

The degree of feasibility to collect, manage and redistribute differs widely between different financing mechanisms. The following recommendations (Landau 2004) apply to every innovative financing mechanism:

1. maximum impact and visibility. This relates to the global public good to be financed;
2. maximum legitimacy. The global good should be well recognized as a *grande cause*;
3. unquestionable equity. This refers to the financing mechanism. Horizontal and vertical equity among agent but also among countries should be taken into account;
4. absolute transparency of the governance of the mechanism;
5. economic efficiency. This implies the cost of implementing the mechanism but also the requirement to make sure the mechanism doesn't produce additional economic distortion.

¹¹ In particular, they developed further the opportunity of *internalising externalities*. This “polluter pays principle” is indicated for global public goods arising from the need to constrain public *bads* such as climate change. For HIV, they limit their analysis to the vaccine.

Figure 2: Financing mechanisms for the Response to HIV

Lamontagne & Greener 2008

b) Other concerns the response to HIV is facing

i) National sovereignty

Governments and parliaments are frequently hesitant to adopt international decisions that might play against their sovereignty or bear some constraining rules that might have negative short term financial impact for the country itself. This is a structural constraint faced by all GPG.

ii) Delivery systems

As we described earlier, the production technology of the response to HIV is not uniform from one activity to another. Research activities are different from Care and Treatment and from prevention activities. So will be the different delivery systems for each set of activities. Nevertheless, For each of them, the following seven elements identified by Sagasti and Bezanson (2001) should be part of the delivery system:

1. Knowledge, public awareness and political decision regarding the good;
2. Global public good regimes. Relate to the nature of the relation between parties;
3. International organizations and partnerships. These partnerships are required in order to promote, monitor, coordinate or even to enforce the provision of the good;
4. Financing mechanisms to provide the good;
5. Operational policies and procedures. Specify how to implement the above regimes;
6. Agreements and contracts. Relate to obligations and rights for national entities regarding production and consumption of the good;
7. Capabilities and arrangements for the inclusion of national and local entities in the provision and consumption of a global public good.

iii) Intellectual property rights (IPR)

Knowledge is recognized as a global public good. So too is research. When the HIV was first identified by Dr Montagnier and his team in 1985, it was the result of shared work between institutes. The knowledge has been made available to all and the fact that Pasteur Institute was working on it did not affect the capability to other laboratories to use this knowledge. Knowledge of this kind is non-excludable and non-rival.

But knowledge can be made excludable by establishing intellectual property rights. Companies are investing in costly research for the development of new molecules and medicines, including antiretroviral drugs (ARV) and vaccines. They expect to recover this investment in the future price of the product. Without any protection, a second company could produce the same medicine at a price that does not include the research cost born by the original investing company. Intellectual property rights prevent this by enabling the inventor to enjoy the returns of its invention during a limited period of time, and thereby ensure that there is an incentive to invest in research.

Intellectual property rights stimulate research, but also create a monopolistic situation in the short term. Since the producer is enabled to practice price discrimination, economic theory predicts that the good will be produced in quantities below its optimal quantity with prices exceeding marginal cost. These factors act as a barrier to the goal of universal access to service – in economic terms the marginal willingness-to-pay of consumers does not equate to the marginal cost of production.

Higher prices raise the issue of equity in access, especially for second-line ARV regimens which have not as yet been subject to the negotiated price decreases seen for first line regimens. As the scale up of ARV continues, so the number of people needing to switch to second line is steadily growing. There is a real possibility that second line therapies at current prices will become what amounts to a club good that is affordable only by better-off patients.

It is important to lower the prices of second line ARV regimens and to increase demand if the goal of universal access by 2010 is to be reached. In September 2006, five countries created a small tax on airplane tickets known as the International Drug Purchasing Facility (UNITAID)¹². This is a promising initiative with clear objectives: to impact market dynamics to lower prices and increase supply through a guaranteed additional demand over a long period. Pooled procurements and direct negotiations with suppliers are expected to reduce the price of drugs closer to their marginal costs.

The World Trade Organization reached an agreement in 1994 on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPs). The HIV epidemic highlighted some of the difficulties the TRIPs could lead to in low and middle-income countries in terms of access to medicines. In light of this, the Doha Declaration was issued in November 2001. The Declaration indicated that TRIPs should not prevent states from dealing with public health crises¹³, an exception that would apply to the manufacture of ARV drugs.

The Doha Declaration was an opportunity for low and middle-income countries to meet some of the challenges to the response to HIV. However, most low and middle income countries have not succeeded to include all of the Doha TRIPs flexibilities such as compulsory licensing, parallel importation, limits on data protection, use of broad research and other exceptions to patentability into their legislation.

The international arbitration and regional negotiations have had some success in reducing prices. Latin America conducted two rounds of ARV price negotiation that led to price reductions for ARV. For example, in 2003 in Lima (Peru), a first sub-regional round of price negotiations involved ten Latin American countries, pharmaceutical companies and generics manufacturers. The negotiation led to a 72% reduction in prices of medicines and diagnostic reagents.

In 2005, a second sub-regional round of price negotiations involving also Brazil, took place in Buenos Aires (Argentina). Additional price reductions of 15 to 55% per line of treatment were reached with laboratories and pharmaceutical companies¹⁴. This kind of initiative could possibly be adapted to other high prevalence regions.

In the current situation, the economies of scale northern laboratories are offering reinforce the *best shot* production technology described earlier. However, researchers from low and middle income countries can play a key role in adapting findings tailored for one wealthy region to another part of the world. For example, it was a manufacturer from a low income country, Cipla in India, who created a triple combination of antiretroviral drug produced in generic form in February 2001. This helped to bring down the price from thirty dollars per patient per day to less than a dollar per day and changed the lives of millions of people. In sum, global public good knowledge should needs to be shared and where there are opportunities for doing so, whether through trade or regional

¹² France, Brazil, Chile, Norway and United Kingdom. See <http://www.unitaid.eu/>

¹³ http://www.wto.org/English/thewto_e/minist_e/min01_e/mindecl_e.htm

¹⁴ See Bermudez J.A.Z., MA Oliveira and GC Chavez (2004)

associations, they should be utilized. Building research partnerships is probably an effective way to overcome future issues with the supply of ARV.

iv) Dismantling or segmentation of the response

In a limited resource environment, a disproportional focus on the provision of one component of the epidemic, like antiretroviral therapy (ARV) will lead to insufficient provision of other components like activities on prevention or impact mitigation. This imbalance bears long-term consequences for the beneficiary country that are often not taken into account by the community of donors, including increased incidence, loss in human capital and loss of productivity. Therefore, the provision of the response to HIV needs to ensure that all activities of the scaling up plans developed by countries are equally implemented.

v) Eradication or control of the epidemic

The current response to HIV is a disease *control* program rather than a disease *eradication* program, with broad global public good implications. The issue would need to be reconsidered if a cure were made available. The economics of the difference between control and eradication¹⁵ has been developed by Barrett (2004a 2004b). A disease control program brings with it a particular challenge in its implementation: as prevalence falls globally, there is less risk for citizens of an individual country to become infected and political support for continuing the response will reduce. Governments may respond by relaxing the control, effectively supplying less of the global public good.

5 The joint products of the response to HIV

A successful response to HIV at global level will halt and reverse the epidemic. However, a successful response will also have other positive outcomes called joint products or positive externalities. A “joint product” can be defined as is a single production process (and set of resources) that yields more than one product at the same time without consuming additional resources. Some of those joint products are an integral part of the response – the contribution to the health sector is probably the most evident example but positive externalities have arisen from other sectors’ as well. Some of these are discussed below.

a) Global concern

The HIV epidemic has re-emphasized a *global concern* that what is happening in developing countries has global repercussions. As a consequence, the world community has realized that there is no reason why people in poor countries should die because they cannot afford the cost of treatments. It was this collective consciousness led by civil society, that led to the pressure on the pharmaceutical industry at the end of the 1990s, leading in turn to reductions in the price of antiretroviral treatments.

b) Community mobilization

The HIV epidemic has boosted community mobilization to a level not achieved so far in health-related issues. National responses to HIV have highlighted the impressive mobilization of

¹⁵ The disease eradication issue is beyond the scope of the current paper and will not be developed here. A disease eradication program is an ambitious goal and Barrett showed that it worth tackling the challenge if a cure is available but the price of the cure is impacting on the rate of vaccination.

communities that would represent a massive financial contribution if the voluntary and benevolent work were costed and quantified¹⁶.

Communities have showed they can successfully conduct activities across the spectrum of HIV programs, including prevention, care for orphans, nutritional support to families, staffing of voluntary counseling and testing (VCT) centers, the fight against stigma and discrimination and provision of health-care. These are examples of successes that other health-related programs could transform into assets and build upon.

c) Partnership

The response to HIV gave birth to new levels of *partnership between private and public actors* that had not hitherto been reached in the health sector. The Global Fund to Fight Aids, Tuberculosis and Malaria (GFATM); the International AIDS Vaccine Initiative (IAVI); the International Drugs Purchasing Facility (UNITAIDS); the unprecedented involvement of philanthropic foundations in programs initially dealt with primarily by international financing institutions; the role of civil society and HIV positive associations in nation-wide programming processes, are some examples of new dimensions of this partnership.

d) A voice to marginalized groups

The Response to HIV has given a *voice to marginalized groups of people whose public health needs have been neglected*: Injecting drug users, sex workers, men who have sex with men or women who are victims of violence or sexual harassment in the workplace.

e) Contribution to the health sector

As a result of HIV, health systems investment has grown and it receives greater attention in national policy and budgeting processes. Data on the direct contribution of HIV Programs to the development of the health sector is lacking and further research is needed – particularly since there is controversy in the direction of the effect.

Many commentators have highlighted the scenario, particularly in least developed countries, of well-resourced facilities for AIDS diagnosis and treatment that coexist with desperately under-resourced facilities for all other services, struggling with lack of equipment, drugs and personnel.

It is important to pinpoint what is most shocking in this asymmetry – it is not the resource allocation to HIV, which is in fact less than what is required, but the lack of resources available for other services and disease related programs. The durable solution lies in actions that focus on how to improve the situation of those other programs whose needs have been neglected by the global community for too long.

As Peter Piot, the Executive Director of UNAIDS has said in his official communication of may 2008, a key challenge here is for us to develop and strengthen effective health systems that can deliver better quality services and improved health to those in need. This is an essential pre-requisite to achieving Universal Access to AIDS treatment.

The response to HIV has confronted an exceptional challenge that partly relates to its position as a global public good: It has succeeded in bringing about a quantum shift upwards in the level of

¹⁶ This is increasingly being recognised among main donors. See for example the GFATM (2007) with its dual track funding mechanism and the World Bank (2008) HIV Agenda for Action 2007-2011.

external assistance, and brought with it the opportunity to enhance the production function for health services, and increase their supply through investments in human resources and health infrastructure. Part of this success is due to the fact that incremental aid funds are coming from sources that are *additional* to official development assistance (ODA), resulting in a shift of the budget constraint.

With respect to human resources in health, HIV has created an increased workload for health workers in high prevalence countries. The response has catalyzed a move away from the traditional health-care model and stimulated adaptations of the workforce in resource-limited settings. An example with applications to other diseases is the Task Shifting model promoted by WHO/UNAIDS/PEPFAR (2007).

In some of the poorer affected countries like Malawi or Zambia, the health systems were often not adequate to address HIV. Those countries developed and put in place specific HIV sub-systems. Where such tailored *vertical* programs have been implemented, it is important to ensure they are gradually integrated into the national health system so that the health system gains can be effectively shared. Further, national HIV programs must take into account the absorptive capacity of existing health systems and adapt their rate of implementation accordingly. These processes are fully supported by UNAIDS¹⁷ as well as WHO, the World Bank and GFATM.

6 Conclusion

There are several definitions of Global public goods. The International Task Force on Global Public Goods has defined global public goods (GPG) as "issues that are broadly conceived as important to the international community, that for the most part cannot or will not be adequately addressed by individual countries acting alone and that are defined through a broad international consensus or a legitimate process of decision-making." Five domains for GPG have been identified, one of which is preventing the emergence and spread of infectious disease.

As a GPG, the response to HIV faces many different challenges, including its provision, the sovereignty of States, its delivery systems, the segmentation of the global response, the necessity to control the epidemic and the price protection resulting from intellectual property rights.

Its provision is the main issue for low and middle-income countries. Countries are asymmetric in their needs of HIV response as they are in their capability to afford the response. Unfortunately, countries with the greatest need are the ones who can afford it the least.

The production of the global response to HIV requires international coordination. The nature of the public good also implies that there is no place for regulation or coercive measures to force contribution from all stakeholders. There is no supranational government and the role of multilateral organizations such as UNAIDS is needed to stimulate the participation of all stakeholders, to maintain the momentum of the response and to assist national efforts to coordinate their response. This role of coordination is of prime importance when the progression of the epidemic starts to reverse: there is a risk for that low-prevalence countries' incentive to contribute to the global response will lower as the risk of being infected inside their own country further reduces.

¹⁷ See UNAIDS (2006), WHO (2003), PAHO (2007), the World Bank (2007b) and Evans (2007) for GFATM

There is room – and need- for every actor in the response at local, national, regional and global levels. As Barrett (2000) pointed out, it is worth focusing on maximizing the contribution of every actor in their respective field of the response, rather than struggling for a lowest common denominator. Every actor has its own comparative advantages, strengths, weaknesses and interests in the response to HIV.

We saw that additional economic factors can further impact the provision of the response. There are risks of substitution effects at different levels. First, for any one country, the national and global levels of the response to HIV may be strategic substitutes. In other terms, as the epidemic appears to be less harmful inside its border, a country might reduce its global response to HIV. The second is related to substitution between different financing channels of the global response to HIV (multilateral vs. bilateral) which might also be substitutes from the point of view of donor countries. Third, there is potential risk of substitution between financing of the response to HIV (and other global public goods) and provision of official development assistance.

Finally, implementing the response to HIV generates joint products or *positive externalities*. We briefly presented five of them: First, the HIV epidemic has raised a global concern about the connections and inequities between the high-income and low-income countries. Second, responding to HIV has exposed the tip of the iceberg that constitutes the remarkable importance of community mobilization. This momentum can and should be pushed forward for other public health issues. Third the response to HIV has given birth to unprecedented partnerships between private and public actors not reached before in the health sector. These partnerships are providing promising opportunities in terms of long term financing for the response to HIV. Fourth, the response has given voice for groups of people whose public health concerns were not sufficiently considered to date. Fifth, the response is expected to contribute to the strengthening of the health sector in low and middle-income countries.

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